

BABUR THE GREAT IS A GREAT PATRIOT

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Abstract : In this article, the spirituality of youth is raised in particular , patriotism , humanitarianism in the spirit in education Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's educational and logical views were discussed on the importance of them today .

Key words: Motherland, patriotism, the Motherland is healthy , the Great Master, tests of fate, sword and pen, poetic images, the situation

Great our grandfather Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur about the word will go since , his in our history and literature incomparable place to catch importance focus it is permissible . Especially the poet classic in our poetry new soul - Motherland and to him was love magnificence kneaded poems attention deserves

Indeed , Babur to his creation look throws there are many of us poems as case in the content is the subject in terms of homeland and to him was longing main to the seat comes out His in his work own life with happiness felt stands : king as per head fell difficulties on paper lowers .

Babur in his work patriotism feeling leader o rinni occupies Poet of the scholars out of ignorance , feudal of tekinkhors from cruelty in verse g sorry to himself loyal three face personality add it with homeland from Andijan out to leave forced will be About this so writes :

What a place to go well done

is inevitable to stay in the state ¹.

Great host basis put big state Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur when it comes to the crisis face caught This is a test to him whole to his life taster og ric point , one lifetime conscience in pain suffering feeling with limmo-lim was Babur fate

tests in front of in awe didn't stay O'z to his homeland return , Farg mother property recovery in the hope o n four year opportunity but waited cruel fate him did not urinate: o ' z his homeland in the eye age , in the heart pain in hand the sword is the pen with leave to leave forced it has been .

From history It is known that Babur was 19 years old Kabul , at the age of 40 India hand enters . where do n't be , mother Homeland healthy him one lifetime leave ca n't

G ' trouts hand even when entering , mag `` defeats even if it 's a face born o scan his homeland add msaydi .

From himself It is known that Babur in our poetry traditional artistic images to the line new images adds , his that 's what's in his work aspects lighting all the time relevance occupation is enough Homeland and sog ' inch , kingdom and poverty , poverty and love , goodness and respect such as poetic images Babur in his work high level expressed image and are concepts . Although Up to Babur this image and of symbols elementary views there is was Although , Babur them limit excellent delivered . It is real to our literature and concrete Homeland image take entered To ' g ' ri , Uzbek in his poetry Even Babur's homeland symbol there is was But if the predecessors in his work Homeland concept in general life , residence do , ro ' zg ' or concepts expressed Babur Homeland means only [Samarkand or Andijan not](#) at all Turkestan understood . O'z in his works his portrait took a picture , finally as a result , of the country artistic image created

Iodine not enough suck person g ' urbat person

Do not rejoice suck please in menat person

I understand this He will not die happily in poverty , oh,

G is on the way don't be happy Sucking , of course , someone says Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur .

Babur fair the king as , dominant was it is also fair in countries politics walked The people to enlightenment , to creativity invited . Spiritual to life negative influence doer of the factors give up past , society in his life them

forbidding put Indian people life and of culture to flourish high contribution added . His own science and knowledge with enlightenment more developed . But life tall [his his mind Homeland](#) , to him was aspiration occupied :

Where ? if you are , oh flower, it is there for soul Babur 's
It's strange tarahhum aylagilkim , andijani .

" God from taallo hope we do that on the ground affairs God please ko ' magi with fast in days saranjom will be It's here affairs to the road down go away , God fate if he does , to ` xtab do n't stop , go to Kabul I'm going down . Of those places grace person how forget ?! Recently to me melon brought were cut when I eat g ' tool effect did I cried a lot " ² .

Homeland the most holy gallows Babur o z his homeland as long as loves , likes . He is with together Homeland Taftini , fragrant bo ' yini take came Melon also belongs to the Motherland one just a tiny bit no , no his so lim meadows , gardens , meadows , and hills reminds

On your way this night is in my heart sadness reached
Vaslingg ' a I didn't have enough , aspect this reached :
Ahem smoke together look at it you are young
Yes mud erdi , yesterday it 's dark it was

It's tonight very sad I was thinking sad was because to you enough I didn't get it . In my mind sadness from that . My country - Motherland to the I couldn't make it because it is yesterday it 's dark , it 's dark while it was mud ³ . A joke is a joke as expression done tragedy analysis who does If so , this is it on the ground mud of the poet eyes young people as a result appear was , that is that's it until many p eyes age because it's enough mud be lib gone , that's it until because he sighed a lot from the mouth came out smoke everyone yes dark i by doing sent by My near me , it seems Babur o z at will opposite in case bitter eyes young people with from the country leaving mud If so , the Timurids of the kingdom to the crisis face catch and history to the stage Shaybanites of silosa come in coming , poet for of darkness - darkness one target was

In general when Babur 's hard work life way , creative activity present in the day to young people lesson to be it is necessary Our spirituality master was this belongs to the great was the nation their children that we are , in our veins Babur passion jo ` sh each of us is beating if we think , if we understand , our hearts really pride feelings cover takes

Babur creativity learn to this again one we will be sure . his jewels the treasure of us Uzbeks our heads sarbaland , we are old upright by doing to walk encourages . We certainly are , Babur such as our ancestors with proud of without

to him worthy successors bring up on the road there is knowledge , experience and our intelligence this on the road mobile to do we are ready

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